

SIMULTANEOUS MEASUREMENT OF STRAIN AND TEMPERAURE FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING USING FBG SENSORS

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SUMMARY

The simultaneous measurement of strain and temperature is necessary for the structural health monitoring of composite structures in various temperature environments. The FBG sensor head is formed by two FBGs, normal and a reverse index FBGs fabricated by different procedure. The FBG sensor head has some merits; the possibility of multiplexing and embedment, the simplicity of measurement system, and more reliability due to no splicing. We evaluated the sensor head analytically and experimentally.

Keywords: composites, fiber Bragg grating, simultaneously measurement

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites have many advantages such as high specific strength, stiffness, corrosion resistance in harsh environment, and the ability to sustain extreme temperature. Therefore the interests in composites have been increasing, and composite structural elements are widely used in making various components for automotive, aerospace, marine, and civil structures [1]. However, the fracture mechanism of composites is very complex under impact and internal damages are not easily detected compared to homogeneous metallic materials. For the reliability of structures, the structural health monitoring technology is necessary to be integrated in the composite structures.

Recently, as the integrated sensing part of composite structures, fiber optic sensors (FOSs) have been widely used due to their convenience of embedment without causing mechanical defects in structures. Especially, fiber Bragg grating sensor (FBG) has the most excellent ability in multiplexing among various FOSs. The Bragg wavelength is expressed as a multiple of the effective refractive index of the Bragg condition grating period [2]. Whenever the grating is exposed to external perturbations, the Bragg wavelength changes. By measuring the wavelength shift, we can calculate the physical properties such as strain and temperature. However, generally the wavelength shift of FBG is happened simultaneously by the effect of strain and temperature in the thermal cycle environment. Therefore, the discrimination of strain and temperature is necessary for the proper structural health monitoring of composite structures.

In recent years, many efforts have been undertaken to develop the discrimination method of strain and temperature. Especially, the wavelength shift of FBG is the change of the grating pitch and the refractive index in the core induced by strain and temperature. There are many discrimination methods of strain and temperature, which are using two FBG with great different wavelengths, two FBGs with different co-dopants, two FBGs with different diameter fiber, two FBGs with one FBG specially packaged, two FBGs with different types, the first order and second order of one FBG, FBG inscribed in polarization-maintaining fiber, hybrid sensor head with FBG and EFPI, FBG and Er⁺ doped fiber, long-period grating, Brillouin distributed sensing, and tilted FBG [3-14]. These methods don't satisfy the all conditions of the possibility of multiplexing and embedment, the simplicity of measurement system, the more reliability, and using the reflective signal.

In this study, the designed FBG head is introduced to measure simultaneously strain and temperature. The FBG sensor head was fabricated by different procedure and analyzed theoretically. The performance verification of the system was carried out in thermal environments and strain levels.

2. FABRICATION AND THEORITICAL ANALYSIS OF FBG HEAD

Generally FBG sensors have the similar strain sensitivities by the mechanical change. On the other hand, their temperature sensitivities are a little different due to each optical refractive index. Therefore FBG sensors with similar refractive index must be annealed to be stable. For sensor multiplexing, the change in Bragg wavelength must be considered. So, we can use the commercial system to measure strain and temperature. For embedment of sensors in composites, the sensors don't have the mechanical extraneous matters such as sensor packaging and substrate and have enough mechanical reliability with no splicing.

The temperature sensitivity is dependent on Bragg wavelength, annealing temperature, and refractive index. In this research, the built FBG sensor was exposed to an UV laser without a phase mask to be a different FBG sensor with the reverse refractive index.

FBG sensors were fabricated in GeO₂/B₂O₃ co-doped fiber (PS1500, Fibercore Co., UK). First, the optical fiber were exposed through the phase mask (IBSEN Co., Denmark) to UV laser at a wavelength of 248 nm from a KrF excimer laser (ASX-750, MPB Co., Canada) to be made into a Bragg grating with the reflectivity of 99 % (20 dB) with gage length of 5 mm. Then after removing the phase mask, the different fiber Bragg gratings were fabricated using UV exposure again to have the reflectivity of 65 % (4.5 dB). UV laser was operated at 10 Hz with the pulse energy of 160 mJ/cm². It took about 10³ times, 1 min 45 sec to be an almost saturated Bragg grating and about 10⁴ times, 16 min 40 sec to be the second Bragg grating. Figure 1 shows the transmitted signal through Bragg grating after removing phase mask. Then normal FBG was fabricated with an interval of 5 cm to make the sensor head.

Figure 1 Transmission signal during fabrication process of inverse FBG.

The Bragg wavelength is dependent on the effective refractive index and the Bragg condition grating period, and the amplitude of the reflection of FBG is dependent on the amplitude of the refractive index modulation in the core of the fiber gratings. The refractive index modulation in the core can be determined in the form [15]

$$\Delta n_{\text{mod}} = \{ \lambda_B / \pi L \eta(V) \} \tanh^{-1} (1 - T_{\text{min}})^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where L is the grating length, η is an overlap function, and T_{min} is the minimum transmission at the Bragg wavelength. The overlap function, η , is expressed by the normalized frequency, V number, from the following:

$$\eta(V) = 1 - 1/V^2 \quad (2)$$

where the V number is determined from the cut-off wavelength, $V = 2.405(\lambda_{\text{cut-off}} / \lambda)$ is 1.849 in $\text{GeO}_2/\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ co-doped fiber. Figure 2 (a) shows the variation of the amplitude of the effective refractive index and the refractive index modulation of the fiber during fabrication process. After removing phase mask, the effective refractive index was increased and the refractive index modulation was decreased until inflection point where the refractive index form along position of optical fiber is reversed from Figure 2 (b). Then the effective refractive index was decreased and the refractive index modulation was gradually increased. This reverse index phenomenon makes that the thermal sensitivity of FBG is changed exponentially.

Figure 2 Refractive index change.

In order to validate the reverse index phenomenon, the numerical simulation on the spectral response of the reverse index FBG (FBG_R) sensor was performed. The governing equations of the Bragg grating under uniform stress were programmed on the basis of equations in the reference [16]. The program calculated the reflected intensity at a certain wavelength point along the gauge length of the Bragg grating from T -matrix formulation for fiber Bragg gratings. For a uniform subgrating of length, ΔL , the T -matrix in Equation (3) can be used with the boundary conditions $a_f(0) = a_0$, $a_b(\Delta L) = a_{\Delta L}$ where a_f and a_b denote the complex amplitudes of forward and backward incident waves in the grating.

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_f(0) \\ a_b(0) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_f(\Delta L) \\ a_b(\Delta L) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The components of the T -matrix are :

$$T_{11} = T_{22}^* = \frac{\Delta\beta \sinh(s\Delta L) + is \cosh(s\Delta L)}{is} \exp(-i\beta_0\Delta L) \quad (4)$$

$$T_{12} = T_{21}^* = \frac{\kappa \sinh(s\Delta L)}{is} \exp(i\beta_0\Delta L) \quad (5)$$

with β representing the propagation constant, $\Delta\beta$ the differential propagation constant, and s the differential coupling coefficient. These parameters are defined as :

$$\Delta\beta \equiv \beta - \beta_0 = \frac{2n\pi}{\lambda} - \frac{\pi}{\Lambda}, \quad s \equiv \sqrt{(|\kappa|^2 - \Delta\beta^2)} \quad (6)$$

where \bar{n} indicates the average effective index of refraction in the grating and κ is the coupling coefficient. This value is generally a complex number and related to the index modulation depth for a uniform grating. For a Gaussian distribution refractive index in the form of :

$$\bar{n}(z) = n_e + \Delta n_{\text{mod}} \exp[-4.41 \{(z - \Lambda/2)/\Lambda\}^2] \quad (7)$$

κ is real and given by,

$$\kappa = \frac{\pi \Delta n_{\text{mod}}}{\lambda} \quad (8)$$

where λ is the wavelength in vacuum, Λ is the optical period, and Δn_e denotes the refractive-index modulation depth of the grating.

In case of a FBG grating with N subgratings, each element can be treated as an independent Bragg grating with its own T -matrix and gauge length. Then the T -matrix equation (11) can be written as :

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_f(0) \\ a_b(0) \end{bmatrix} = [T(\Delta L_1)] [T(\Delta L_2)] \cdots [T(\Delta L_N)] \begin{bmatrix} a_f(L_G) \\ a_b(L_G) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $L_G = \Delta L_1 + \Delta L_2 + \cdots + \Delta L_N$.

The transmissivity of reverse FBG in numerical analysis in figure 3 is similar with the transmission signal during fabrication process of inverse index FBG.

Figure 3 Spectrum change of reverse FBG in numerical analysis.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

The methods with two FBGs use the different sensitivity of strain and temperature of two FBG. Assuming that the strain and thermal perturbations are linear, the Bragg wavelength $\Delta\lambda_\varepsilon$ and $\Delta\lambda_T$, in response to a strain change $\Delta\varepsilon$ and temperature change ΔT , can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\lambda_\varepsilon &= K_\varepsilon \Delta\varepsilon \\ \Delta\lambda_T &= K_T \Delta T\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

where K_ε is the strain sensitivity and K_T is the temperature sensitivity. K_ε is related to the Poisson ration of the fiber, the photoelastic coefficient, and the effective refractive index of the fiber core and K_T is determined by the thermal expansion coefficient and the thermo-optic coefficient. As the photoelastic and thermo-optic coefficients are wavelength dependent, fractional wavelength changes of each of the two superimposed gratings will be different although each grating is subject to the same level of strain or temperature. In general, the change in Bragg wavelength of the fiber grating $\Delta\lambda_B$, due to a combination of strain and temperature, can be expressed as

$$\Delta\lambda_B(\varepsilon, T) = K_\varepsilon \Delta\varepsilon + K_T \Delta T \quad (11)$$

As a result, for the two wavelengths to be measured, the following equation holds:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta\lambda_{B1} \\ \Delta\lambda_{B2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} K_{\varepsilon1} & K_{T1} \\ K_{\varepsilon2} & K_{T2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\varepsilon \\ \Delta T \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The sensor heads were placed next to thermo couple (Omega, USA) with a Tefron tape on the Pyrex bottle into the oven. The experimental setup for the thermal sensitivity of the sensor heads are represented in Figure 4. The wavelength shifts of the sensor heads were measured by the commercial FBG interrogator (IS7000, Fibepro co., Korea) with the resolution of ± 1 pm. The temperature in the oven was increased until 150°C gradually. Before the experiment, the sensor head were annealed at 170°C during 24 hours for the stable of the thermal sensitivity. The signals of the wavelength shifts were obtained during experiment at a sampling rate of 100MS/s.

The Bragg wavelength of the reverse index FBG and the normal FBG were dependent on the temperature change in Figure 5. The non-linear temperature response arising from the thermo-optic coefficient, within the temperature range between 20°C and 150°C is shown. From the experimental results, the thermal sensitivity of reverse index

FBG was calculated to be $10.14 \pm 0.0726 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and that of normal FBG was $9.35 \pm 0.0424 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 4 Experimental setup for thermal sensitivity.

Figure 5 Temperature sensitivity of proposed sensor system.

Table 1 Calculated error of the temperature sensitivity

Grating label	$K_T \text{ (pm}/^\circ\text{C)}$	Error (pm/ $^\circ\text{C}$)
FBG _N	9.35	± 0.0424
FBG _R	10.14	± 0.0726

Strain characterization is tested using a micro positioner. The wavelength shifts of the sensor heads were also acquired by the commercial FBG interrogator until 7000 $\mu\epsilon$. As the mechanical strain changes a same variation in the grating pitch in the same fiber, the similar variations of the wavelength shifts were obtained in the figure 7. Therefore, the strain sensitivity of the sensor head was calculated to be 1.2 ± 0.004 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$.

Figure 7 Strain sensitivity of proposed sensor system.

Table 2 Calculated error of the strain sensitivity

Grating label	K_{ϵ} (pm/ $\mu\epsilon$)	Error (pm/ $\mu\epsilon$)
FBG _N	1.2	± 0.004
FBG _R	1.2	± 0.004

3. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the sensor head simultaneously to measure strain and temperature has been designed and tested. The sensor head is formed by two FBGs formed side by side normal and a reverse index FBGs fabricated by different procedure. The fabrication of the reverse index FBG was studied and reverse index phenomena was analyzed theoretically. Then the performance verification of the system with this sensor head was carried out in thermal environments and strain levels. The condition number of the sensor head for an evaluation of a sensor system is not the most sensitive system. Because of the possibility of the multiplexing and the embedment, the simplicity of the measurement system just like using commercial systems, the more higher reliability with no splicing, and the measurement of the reflection of Bragg wavelength, this sensor system could be the most useful for the simultaneous measurement of strain and temperature within a host composite material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work was supported by Agency for Defense Development in Korea (project No. UC080019JD). This support is gratefully acknowledged.

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